

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF 2D-SiC/BN/SiC PROCESSED BY ICVI

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical behavior and the interfacial properties of 2D ¹Nicalon™/BN/SiC composites processed by ICVI were investigated by means of tensile tests, unloading-reloading and fatigue cycles at room temperature but also by flexure static fatigue in oxidative atmosphere. High strength and strain have been found for various interphase thicknesses deposited on treated Nicalon™ fibers. The results have been compared, when data were available, to a composite with a pyrocarbon interphase. SiC/BN/SiC composites have proved to be more efficient than SiC/C/SiC materials when stress is applied in aggressive environment but they present a lower dynamic fatigue resistance which could be attributed to different interfacial properties.

INTRODUCTION

High fracture strength and strain have been obtained in ceramic or glass-ceramic matrix composites, particularly when a compliant interphase is present between the fiber and the matrix [1]. While in some cases, a tough carbon-rich sublayer forms *in situ* during composite fabrication due to chemical interactions between the fiber and the matrix precursors [1-2], this interphase does not exist in most of the composite systems. Therefore fiber coating, generally deposited by chemical vapor deposition processes prior to matrix deposition, has been used resulting in a non-brittle mechanical behavior [1-3]. Carbon interphases are commonly utilized in CMC but their drawbacks in oxidative environments are obvious. Boron nitride has been proposed as an alternative, because it crystallizes in the hexagonal system with a lamellar structure like graphite, and it is more oxidation resistant. Strong and tough composites with a BN interphase deposited by chemical vapor processes on Nicalon™-SiC fibers have been successfully fabricated [2, 4-6]. In any case, the ultimate strength at room temperature remained rather below the value obtained for a composite of similar composition but with a pyrocarbon (PyC) interphase. It is established that the weakest link in such composites is generally located at the fiber/BN interface [2, 4, 6-7]. This interfacial zone can be complex and it may consist, besides the interphase itself, of very thin sublayers mainly composed of carbon and silica, either as separated or mixed phases. They can result from the manufacture of the fiber itself or from gas-solid or solid-solid interaction during the interphase and matrix manufacturing [2]. The presence and the evolution of these sublayers can strongly influence the thermomechanical properties of the material.

¹ Nicalon™ : Nippon Carbon, Japan.

In this work the mechanical behavior at room temperature of SiC/SiC composite has been examined as a function of different characteristics of the interface between Nicalon™ fibers and a BN interphase made by ICVI from $\text{BCl}_3\text{-NH}_3\text{-H}_2$ mixtures. The influence of the interphase thickness which can change the interfacial bonding is also reported. Cyclic unloading-reloading experiments were carried out in the non-linear stress-strain domain up to failure. The composites were also tested in air at 600°C, using four-point bending tests, at different stresses ranging from 150 to 250 MPa. The results are compared to the results obtained with a pyrocarbon interphase.

MATERIALS

The materials used in the present investigation were prepared from 2D-SiC preforms made of Nicalon™ fibers. They consisted of stacks of Nicalon™ plain-weave fabrics pressed together with a graphite tool to maintain a constant nominal fiber content of about 37 vol%. The size of the fibrous preform was $160 \times 80 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$. The fibers surface was of two different types. The first type corresponds to the untreated NLM 202 Nicalon™ fiber whose surface is irregular and composed of silica with some amounts of free carbon [8]. Another type was obtained after a treatment (proprietary treatment), carried out by the Société Européenne de Propulsion (SEP); the treated fiber presents a different composition over a significant thickness and the surface is now rich in free carbon [9]. It has been verified that this treatment does not decrease the mechanical properties of the NLM 202 Nicalon™ fibers at room temperature.

The fibers were coated with a BN film by isothermal/isobaric chemical vapor infiltration prior to the SiC matrix infiltration. $\text{BCl}_3\text{-NH}_3\text{-H}_2$ gas mixtures were used at a temperature of 973 K and a reactor pressure of about 1.33 kPa, according to a procedure which is described elsewhere [10]. The deposition time was chosen to attain first a thickness of 0.5 μm on both untreated and treated fibers. Three other interphase thicknesses (0.7, 0.4 and 0.2 μm) were also processed on 2D-preforms made with treated fibers. Densification of all these preforms by silicon carbide was then carried out at SEP by a classical ICVI process from $\text{H}_2\text{-CH}_3\text{SiCl}_3$ (MTS) mixtures.

MECHANICAL TESTS

The mechanical behavior of the 2D composites was evaluated at room temperature by tensile testing. The properties of the interfaces and interphases and their evolution due to the repeated slidings between the components were investigated by performing unloading-reloading and fatigue cycles.

The geometry and dimensions of the tensile specimens are presented in Fig. 1. The test bars were cut parallel to one of the fibers orientation. The tensile tests at room temperature were performed on an electromechanical machine (1186 Instron) equipped with hydraulic grips. The crosshead speed was 0.2 mm/min during the elastic behavior of the composite and was subsequently increased to 0.5 mm/min. The tensile strain was measured with an extensometer (2620-603 Instron) with a 25 mm gauge length. The unloading-reloading cycles were carried out with a constant strain increment of 0.1 % up to failure. The fatigue behavior was studied in tension-tension on a hydraulic machine (Instron Dynamic 8501) equipped with hydraulic grips. The test frequency was adjusted at the desired value, in the present case 20 Hz, after a few cycles at 0.02 Hz. The mechanical behavior in an oxidizing environment, i.e., air at 600°C, was evaluated in static fatigue. The tests were performed on a 4-point bending SEP machine prototype having major and minor spans of 5.08 cm and 2.54 cm. The specimens thickness was again 3 mm.

RESULTS

It has been first verified on monofilaments that no mechanical degradation of the fibers was induced by the deposition of BN from the $\text{BCl}_3\text{-NH}_3\text{-H}_2$ mixture. These results together with the properties of 1D microcomposites are reported elsewhere [11].

2D-SiC/BN/SiC MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Tensile strength

A minimum of two specimens of each material were tested. The average tensile properties of the composites and their standard deviation are summarized in Table 1. Typical stress-strain curves for the two types of Nicalon™/BN/SiC composites with a 0.5 μm BN interphase are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 : Geometry and dimensions of the tensile specimens.

Table 1 : Mechanical properties of 2D-Nicalon™/BN/SiC composites processed by ICVI for untreated and treated fibers and for different interphase thicknesses.

BN thickness	Nicalon™ fibers	Failure properties			density
		σ MPa	ε %	E GPa	
0.5 μm	untreated	170 {20}	0.3 {0.1}	180 {10}	2.20 {0.07}
	treated	290 {10}	1.1 {0.2}	175 {5}	2.24 {0.04}
0.7 μm	treated	300 {30}	1.3 {0.1}	155 {5}	2.13 {0.04}
0.4 μm	treated	320 {30}	1.1 {0.1}	205 {5}	2.55 {0.05}
0.2 μm	treated	305 {35}	1.0 {0.2}	220 {10}	2.55 {0.05}

The treatment of the Nicalon™ fibers clearly defines two characteristic behaviors. The strength measured with the untreated Nicalon™ clothes are in good agreement with the results obtained for typical Nicalon™/BN/SiC composites [2]. Composites manufactured with the treated fibers exhibit higher tensile properties that are close to the properties of materials with a PyC interphase. In both cases, the composites present a non-brittle behavior. After an initial linear region, the stress-strain curves exhibit a non linear behavior corresponding to the matrix cracking developing in the material (Fig. 2).

As a function of the above results, further investigations on the influence of the BN thickness have only been carried out with treated Nicalon™ fibers. A change in the interphase thickness from 0.7 to 0.2 μm did not reveal any notable variation in the tensile strength as shown in Table 1. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note the particular shape of the stress-strain curve only obtained with a BN thickness of 0.2 μm (Fig. 2). This plateau-like feature is usually attributed to weaker interfacial bonding and early microcrack saturation stage in the matrix.

Fig. 2: Tensile stress-strain curves for 2D-SiC/BN/SiC composites with untreated (---) and treated fibers (—) both with $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ BN and treated fibers with $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ BN (-.-)

Fig. 3: Tensile stress-strain curves with unloading-reloading cycles for materials with $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ BN

Unloading-Reloading Cycles

Tensile tests with periodic unloading-reloading cycles were performed on all composites. Due to matrix cracking and the resulting debonding-sliding phenomena, a decrease of the elastic modulus as well as hysteresis loops (Fig. 3) were developing as further load was applied.

For all materials, the onset of non linearity takes place at a stress of about 60-80 MPa. The composites with a BN interphase show rather large hysteresis loops and permanent strain, suggestive of rather weak interfacial properties. A methodology to assess the actual constituents properties of CMC's from hysteresis loop measurements has been recently developed [13] and applied to unidirectional and 2D composites [14]. Thanks to the evaluation of few parameters, the elastic modulus of the composite upon unloading E^* , the inelastic strain index \mathcal{L} and the debond stress σ_i , information can be obtained about the crack density evolution, the interface sliding stress τ and the interfacial debond energy Γ_i . For unidirectional material, \mathcal{L} is inversely proportional to τ and the crack density. Previous works [12-14] suggested that the crack density has a rather linear evolution with the applied stress which implied a linear evolution of \mathcal{L} as well as E^* with the applied stress. Therefore, it is the type of representation that has been chosen and is shown in Figs. 4-5 where \mathcal{L} and σ_i are given as a function of the peak stress σ_p . As the analysis is thoroughly described elsewhere [12-14], it is readily applied in this work, without further development.

The analysis performed on the four composites is detailed in the case of the $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ interphase. Furthermore, the results are compared with those obtained by Domergue et al. [13] on corresponding SiC/C/SiC composites, manufactured by SEP with a pyrocarbon interphase deposited on treated NicalonTM fibers. It can be seen from the evolution of the elastic modulus and the inelastic strain index (Fig. 4) that both of those values no more increase after a stress of about 200-220 MPa, suggesting that saturation of the crack density has been reached at this stress level. In contrast, similar representations for the materials with the thickest BN interphases do not show such saturation value. These results suggest that the crack density is constantly increasing as further load is applied. It might be interesting to point out that the crack spacing at failure is $25 \mu\text{m}$ for the $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ interphase compared to $50 \mu\text{m}$ for the $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ interphase. The combination of those crack spacing measurements and the evolution of \mathcal{L} imply that the

interfacial shear stress increases with the interphase thickness. On the other hand, Fig. 5 suggests that the debonding energy is not influenced by the thickness of the interphase. This could rationalize the difference in behavior between the materials (in particular the early saturation and the higher crack spacing for the material with the thinnest interphase).

Fig. 4 : Variations in the inelastic strain index L with peak stress for 2D SiC/SiC composites with a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ BN interphase compared with a similar 2D SiC/C/SiC material.

Fig. 5 : Debond stress measured for 2D SiC/SiC composites with various interphases.

Fatigue Strength

The fatigue tests were only carried out, at different stress levels, on two composites manufactured with treated Nicalon™ fibers coated with a $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ BN interphase. A 20 Hz frequency was chosen for the experiments. The first sample was loaded between 0 and 150 MPa during 1.6×10^6 cycles, then the load was increased to 200 MPa. The composite broke after 700 cycles at this load level. The results have been compared when it was possible to composites of similar composition but with a PyC interphase (Table 2). The second sample has passed 4.6×10^6 cycles between 0 and 120 MPa ; then its ultimate tensile strength was measured at 270 MPa with a strain of 0.9 %.

Table 2 : Fatigue in tension-tension at 20 Hz for a 2D Nicalon™/BN/SiC composite with a $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ BN interphase compared to a composite of similar composition with a PyC interphase (SEP results).

R indicates a rupture of the composite, NR indicates no rupture.

	Nature of the interphase	
	0 - 200 MPa	700 cycles R
0 - 150 MPa	$1.6 \cdot 10^6$ cycles NR	$1.6 \cdot 10^6$ cycles NR

Fig. 6 : Static fatigue behavior in flexion for 2D SiC/SiC composites with various interphases deposited on treated Nicalon™ fibers.

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION AT 600°C IN AIR

The 2D-SiC/BN/SiC composites fabricated with treated Nicalon™ fibers and various interphases thicknesses of 0.7, 0.4 and 0.2 μm were selected for further static fatigue testing in air at 600°C. Two specimens of each composite were tested using a constant applied load to determine the time to cause specimen fracture as a function of the applied stress. The minimum time to cause failure of composites with different BN thicknesses as well as a pyrocarbon interphase is plotted in Fig. 6. Both samples of the composite made with a 0.2 μm BN interphase were not fractured after more than 310 hours at 150 MPa.

DISCUSSION

Although the tough mechanical behavior is obtained by intentional fabrication of the interphase, the FM interfacial zone consists of additional sublayers and interfaces [2]. Then the location of the weakest link is of prime importance; it is often found at the interface between the fiber and the interphase [2, 4, 6-7]. Therefore the nature of the constituents of this interface governs the thermomechanical behavior of the material. Even if decohesions were observed between the matrix and the interphase in the SiC/BN/SiC composites [11], cracks that occurred in the matrix were more often deflected at the Nicalon™ fiber/BN interface. By contrast, in the similar SiC/C/SiC composite, the debonding was taking place within the interphase [9].

Untreated fibers, whose surface is irregular and composed with silica and some amount of free carbon, have led to early failure at a low strain. As it was found on monofilaments that the BN deposition never involved an important alteration of the mechanical properties of the Nicalon™ fiber (treated or not), the early failure of these 2D composites could be attributed to a too strong FM bonding. This bonding can be related to an irregular fiber surface that hinder the fiber pull-out and also probably to a strong chemical bonding between the fiber and the interphase which could be produced during the deposition process or by solid-solid interaction. Thermodynamic calculations do not predict an important interaction between the silica and the inlet gaseous mixture employed here for BN deposition. Nevertheless, it is well known that infiltration conditions may involve an equilibrium departure, especially at low deposition temperature, which can modify the equilibrium predictions. Moreover, oxygen is always present in the deposition reactor as impurity and at the fiber surface. Therefore numerous solid phases that contain oxygen and nitrogen could lead, in this B-N-Si-O system, to a strong link between silica and boron nitride at the interface between the fiber and the interphase.

The treatment of the fiber permits to improve the mechanical behavior of the composite. Thus, high strength and high strain have been obtained with 2D SiC/BN/SiC composites that are close to the characteristics to failure of 2D SiC/C/SiC materials. The better behavior observed for SiC/BN/SiC composites based on treated Nicalon™ fabrics could be attributed to the thin carbon-rich film at the fiber surface. For this reason, a variation of the interphase thickness in the range 0.2-0.7 μm has not induced drastically different mechanical and interfacial properties even if the materials with a BN interphase thicker than 0.2 μm seem to present higher sliding resistance. Compared to SiC/C/SiC, materials with a BN interphase have weaker sliding resistance even if their debonding properties seem to be similar. This fact is not clearly understood but could be related to the thin carbon-rich layer that is present at the fiber/BN interface or more simply to some limitation of the model. The better behavior towards unloading-reloading cycles of the composites made with treated Nicalon™ fibers and the pyrocarbon interphase is confirmed by the tension-tension fatigue tests at room temperature.

On the other hand the static fatigue tests at 600°C in air show the better oxidation resistance of SiC/SiC composites with a BN interphase when compared to the PyC one. The failure of the composite appears all the later since the applied stress and the interphase thickness are low. The

first result is obviously due to the influence of the crack opening which is directly correlated to strain. When the stress increases, oxygen diffuses more easily into the composite till the fiber/BN interface. Then, we can assumed that the thin carbon layer is consumed leading schematically to an annular pore around each fiber or a glassy layer as already suggested by Vix-Guterl [15]. Either the load transfer becomes inefficient or the FM-bonding becomes too strong but in any case the composite rapidly breaks. The role of the interphase thickness seems not so simple when both the mechanical behaviors at room temperature and at 600°C are examined. A more thorough study of the influence of the interphase thickness on other parameters like the sublayers thickness, the nature of the interfaces, and the residual stresses in various parts of the composites would be necessary. The influence of the temperature on the thermal component of the residual stresses should also be taken into account to try to explain the results at 600°C.

CONCLUSIONS

Some mechanical properties of one of the most promising ceramic-matrix material for high temperature structural applications, i.e., SiC/SiC composite are presented here. Since boron nitride has been proposed as an alternative to PyC, few results have been reported on the thermomechanical behavior of SiC/BN/SiC composites. It is shown here that high strength and high strain have been obtained for SiC/BN/SiC composites fabricated with particular conditions. First the Nicalon™ fiber has been treated leading to a smooth carbon-rich surface instead of the irregular and silica-rich one. Secondly a BN interphase has been deposited by ICVI from $\text{BCl}_3\text{-NH}_3\text{-H}_2$ mixtures at moderate temperature. Thus, the macroscopic stress-strain behavior is similar to the results obtained with a PyC interphase. However, the crack deflection mechanism is different for the two types of composites. The debonding always appears between the BN interphase and the fiber in SiC/BN/SiC materials whereas it occurs within the pyrocarbon interphase deposited on treated Nicalon™ fibers in similar SiC/C/SiC composite. BN interphase thicknesses superior to 0.2 μm do not reveal drastically different mechanical behavior and interfacial properties at room temperature while the thinnest interphase leads to weaker sliding resistance. Finally, larger hysteresis loops and permanent strain and, more importantly, a weaker fatigue resistance at room temperature are found for SiC/BN/SiC composites, especially for the thinnest interphase.

On the other hand, the better behavior of the SiC/BN/SiC composites in oxidative atmosphere has been confirmed by static fatigue tests. Present investigations are in progress to explain the fact that thinner interphase leads to better retention of the mechanical strength. Additionally, the composition and the microstructure of the interphase and the interfaces are characterized as well as the microcracking and the deflection mode. Finally, interfacial modelizations, which become increasingly helpful for the optimization of the process, have still to be refined to take into account the specific properties of the different constituents of the interfacial sequences at a micro or nanoscale. The influence of the temperature of the material on its interfacial properties should also be considered.

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